

Interlaboratory Comparison of Two-Dimensional Magnetic Measurements

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ABSTRACT

We compare alternating and rotational energy loss measurements performed by three laboratories (INRIM, Politecnico di Torino, and Ampère Lab. at Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1) using Rotational Single Sheet Testers (RSSTs) on 0.30 mm thick non-oriented (NO) Fe–Si sheets. Different magnetizing setups and sample geometries have been adopted. The measurements performed with circular polarization loci have been supplemented by alternating loss tests carried out under alternating sinusoidal polarization by the RSST, the standard Epstein frame, and the single strip tester with H -coil. The peak polarization value ranged between 1 T and 1.5 T in the 5 Hz - 200 Hz frequency interval. The critical role of the sensing area and the thickness and geometrical perfection of the bi-dimensional H -coils employed in detecting the effective field at the sample surface is highlighted. The dispersion among the results obtained in the different laboratories is discussed.

Keywords: One and two-dimensional magnetic loss, Loss intercomparison, Rotational Single Sheet Tester

INTRODUCTION

The IEC standard methods adopted for electrical steel characterization, such as the Epstein frame (IEC 60404-2) and the Single Sheet Tester (SST) (IEC 60404-3), are devoted to the reproducible measurement of the magnetic properties under one-dimensional supply conditions. However, the optimal design of electrical machines and devices would be favoured further if the material behavior under complex supply conditions could be recognized in theory and practice. There are indeed methods to recover the energy loss figure under either distorted or generically non-sinusoidal flux [1-4], but a general approach to the problem of magnetic loss calculation in electrical machines would also require methods to treat the material response under two-dimensional (2D) excitation. The nuclei of the rotating electrical machines are, in fact, always affected by 2D flux loci, partly accounted for in the calculations by resorting to an empirical building factor.

Since the 80s, methods and setups known as Rotational Single Sheet Testers (RSST) have been developed for the 2D characterization of magnetic sheets [5 – 9]. However, past international comparisons of rotational power losses in grain-oriented (GO) and non-oriented (NO) Fe–Si sheets showed a large dispersion of the measured figures, with differences ranging from a few per cent to more than 40 %, both in GO and NO sheets [10]. A better agreement was later obtained in a two-lab comparison made on NO sheets between 10 Hz and 100 Hz [11]. These exercises, however, lacked any reference to absolute loss figures, as one could obtain, for example, by testing the same laminations via calibrated equipment according to standard methods (e.g., by the Epstein test frame). Since the 2D measurements involve determining the effective magnetizing field and the induction derivative across a limited portion of the sheet sample, where the spatial uniformity of these quantities may not be ensured, no certainty exists about the closeness to the true loss value.

Consequently, the requirement of reproducible RSST results among laboratories should possibly be accompanied by an estimate of their absolute accuracy. The interlaboratory comparison discussed started with determining the loss figure under alternating field and sinusoidal induction. To this end, the standard measurements using the Epstein test frame were paired and compared with a single-strip approach, where the effective field is retrieved on the strip surface by a flat H -coil, close to a localized secondary winding, and the true loss figure is expectedly obtained [12-13]. These measurements were repeated, on samples taken from the same parent strip, with the laboratories RSST magnetizers and the systematic differences of the alternating loss figures with respect to the reference ones were recorded. The frequency range $5 \text{ Hz} \leq f \leq 200 \text{ Hz}$ was investigated at the peak polarization values $J_p = 1.0, 1.25, 1.4, \text{ and } 1.5 \text{ T}$. All laboratories adopted the fieldmetric technique [1]. Systematic differences up to a maximum 7 % were observed between the best RSST alternating loss values and the reference loss figures, while the laboratory-to-laboratory differences, depending on J_p and f , ranged between $\pm 7 \%$. Measurements under circular induction were also carried out under the same frequency range and peak amplitudes. The analysis of the reproducibility showed laboratory-to-laboratory differences, depending on J_p and f , ranging between $\pm 5 \%$.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND SETUPS

0.30 mm thick NO Fe-(3.5wt%)Si laminations (density 7600 kg/m^3 , resistivity $56.9 \times 10^{-8} \text{ } \Omega \cdot \text{m}$) were characterized in the three different laboratories. INRIM and Ampère Lab adopted circular samples (diameter 80-78 mm) and stator-like magnetizers (three-phase versus two-phase) with a 1 mm air gap. PoliTO characterized cross-shaped samples with an 80 mm wide central area, excited employing double-C yokes. The three laboratories used the field-metric method to characterise the specimen (hysteresis loop and energy loss). The method is based on the measurement of the magnetic field components at the sample surface (H_x, H_y) and the associated inductions (B_x, B_y), where x and y are two orthogonal axes in the lamination plane, corresponding to the Rolling (RD) and the Transverse (TD) directions. The induction components (B_x, B_y) are detected employing centered orthogonally wound few-turn coils threaded through small (0.5-0.75 mm) holes, drilled symmetrically on the measuring region. The detected voltages [$V_{B_x}(t), V_{B_y}(t)$] provide the inductions as

$$B_x(t) = \frac{1}{N_x S_x} \left(\int_0^t V_{B_x}(t') dt' - \langle \int_0^t V_{B_x}(t') dt' \rangle_T \right) \quad (1)$$

$$B_y(t) = \frac{1}{N_y S_y} \left(\int_0^t V_{B_y}(t') dt' - \langle \int_0^t V_{B_y}(t') dt' \rangle_T \right) \quad (2)$$

where N_x and N_y are the number of turns of the B -windings and S_x , and S_y are their cross-sectional areas.

The tangential field components H_x and H_y are detected through two crossed multi-turn flat H-coils wound on the same rigid thin epoxy plate (thickness $d \sim 1 \text{ mm}$ or less) and firmly attached to the specimen surface. The induced voltages V_{H_x} and V_{H_y} are linked to the magnetic field through the equations

$$H_x(t) = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \frac{1}{(N \cdot A)_x} \left(\int_0^t V_{H_x}(t') dt' - \langle \int_0^t V_{H_x}(t') dt' \rangle_T \right) \quad (3)$$

$$H_y(t) = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \frac{1}{(N \cdot A)_y} \left(\int_0^t V_{H_y}(t') dt' - \langle \int_0^t V_{H_y}(t') dt' \rangle_T \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\langle * \rangle_T$ is the time average over the period T ; $(NA)_x$ and $(NA)_y$ [m^2] are the turn-area products obtained through calibration of the H-coils via a reference solenoid. B and H coils occupied a centered $20 \text{ mm} \times 20 \text{ mm}$ sensing area.

The energy loss [J/m^3] is obtained from the measured field and induction components according to the formula

$$W = \int_0^T \left(H_x \frac{dB_x}{dt} + H_y \frac{dB_y}{dt} \right) dt \quad (5)$$

The desired 2D flux locus is controlled through on-purpose developed digital feedback procedures.

To remark here the unavoidable approximation involved with measuring the effective field in an open sample, with its large and relatively inhomogeneous demagnetizing field. On the one hand, by the H -coil one tends to overestimate the effective field, because of its finite thickness. This fact, however, feebly interferes, in principle, with the loss measurement, because true and measured fields differ by a quantity proportional to the magnetization. On the other hand, some inaccuracy of the field-metric two-dimensional (2D) loss measurement can derive from possible slight misalignment and imperfect orthogonality of the H - and B - windings. When measured with the field rotating clockwise (CW) or counterclockwise (CCW), this leads to different loss values. This discrepancy can be largely, though not fully, compensated by averaging the results of the CW and CCW measurements.

The setup developed at INRIM is a two-pole/three-phase RSST (Fig. 1). It was designed using 3D FEM analysis, considering the specifications of the supply system, with the geometry optimized for an 80 mm diameter sample. The core of the magnetizer is made by stacking 0.35 mm thick non-oriented Fe-Si sheets. The three-phase winding is toroidal, distributed over three slots per pole. The circular sample is separated from the magnetizing core by a 1 mm thick gap, permitting one to minimize the apparent power required by the magnetizer. The magnetizer is driven by three 5 kVA DC-coupled CROWN AUDIO 5000VZ power amplifiers (peak-to-peak output voltage 300 V, maximum output current 40 A), controlled by three synchronized Agilent 33220A function generators. The V_{B_x} , V_{B_y} , V_{H_x} , and V_{H_y} signals, detected on a central $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$ sensing area, are amplified by SRS-560 DC- 1 MHz low-noise pre-amplifiers and fed to a four-channel 150 Msample/s Tektronix TDS-420 digital oscilloscope. Synchronous sampling over all the channels is made at effective 14-bit resolution at the investigated frequencies. A feedback algorithm based on the contraction mapping principle [2], operating in a VEE environment, is implemented, in order to impose the desired sinusoidal $V_{B_x}(t)$ and $V_{B_y}(t)$ waveforms.

Figure 1. The two-pole/three-phase RSST setup (a) was employed at INRIM with the geometry optimized for an 80 mm diameter sample. The toroidal windings are distributed over three slots per pole (b).

The Ampère Laboratory used a two-phase stator-like RSST (internal diameter 80 mm, height 35 mm, 1 mm air gap), allowing to host disk samples of diameter up to 78 mm (see Fig. 2a). Semi-circular notches (3 mm wide) on the periphery of the sample receive vertical axes to ensure angular positioning. A two-channel arbitrary function generator drives the magnetic excitation on both stator windings through power amplifiers and scaling transformers. The magnetic flux density B is read using 20 mm B -coils woven (3 turns) through holes (20 mm apart) in the sample, and the magnetic field H is measured by stacked tangential PCB coils ($18 \times 18 \text{ mm}^2$, 30 turns). The induced voltages in the coils are magnified by high-bandwidth amplifiers and digitized by a synchronous acquisition card with the input voltages. A software operates the test bench, communicating with the acquisition and generation devices, signal processing, and B waveform control. An overview of the whole setup is shown in Fig. 2b.

Figure 2. The Ampère Laboratory used a two-phase stator-like RSST (internal diameter 80 mm, height 35 mm, 1 mm air gap), allowing to host disk samples of diameter up to 78 mm (see Fig. 2a). Semi-circular notches (3 mm wide) on the periphery of the sample receive vertical axes to ensure angular positioning. A 2-channels arbitrary function generator drives the magnetic excitation on both stator windings through power amplifiers and scaling transformers. The magnetic flux density B is read using 20 mm B -coils woven (3 turns) through holes (20 mm apart) in the sample, and the magnetic field H is measured by stacked tangential PCB coils ($18 \times 18 \text{ mm}^2$, 30 turns). The induced voltages in the coils are magnified by high-bandwidth amplifiers and digitized by a synchronous acquisition card with the input voltages. A software operates the test bench, communicating with the acquisition and generation devices, signal processing, and B waveform control. An overview of the whole setup is shown in Fig. 2b.

PoliTO characterized cross-shaped samples with 80 mm wide central area employing a RSST with two perpendicular C-yokes (Fig. 3a). The yoke dimensions (Fig. 3b) are length $l = 200 \text{ mm}$, width $w = 80 \text{ mm}$, and thickness $t = 20 \text{ mm}$. The two yokes have 100 mm and 130 mm high limbs. Each of them is supplied by two 60-turn series-connected windings. The induction derivative and the tangential field components were detected employing centred orthogonally wound two-turn induction coils, see Fig. 3c, (holes diameter = 0.5 mm; wire diameter = 0.1 mm) and flat 300-turn H -coils (epoxy board thickness = 1 mm; wire diameter = 0.05 mm). The sensing coils occupy a $20 \text{ mm} \times 20 \text{ mm}$ sensing area (red square in Fig. 3c), where the field and induction are almost uniform. The exact product of the number of turns and cross-section area of the H coils were calibrated. As shown in Fig. 4, the integrated system includes a computer, a dual-channel waveform generator (KEYSIGHT 33500B), two power amplifiers (KEPCO BOP 50-8D), a four-channel input oscilloscope (TELEDYNE LECROY MDA805A), and four signal amplifiers.

Figure 3. The PoliTO lab characterized cross-shaped samples with an 80 mm wide central area (see Fig. 3a) employing an RSST adopting two perpendicular C-yokes. The yoke dimensions (Fig. 3b) are length $l = 200 \text{ mm}$, width $w = 80 \text{ mm}$, and thickness $t = 20 \text{ mm}$. The two yokes have 100 mm and 130 mm high limbs. Each of them is supplied by two 60-turn series-connected windings. The sensing coils occupy a $20 \text{ mm} \times 20 \text{ mm}$ area (red square in Fig. 3c), where the field and induction are almost uniform.

Figure 4. Overview of the RSST developed at PoliTO. The integrated system includes a computer, a dual-channel waveform generator (KEYSIGHT 33500B), two power amplifiers (KEPCO BOP 50-8D), a four-channel input oscilloscope (TELEDYNE LECROY MDA805A), and four signal amplifiers. The computer generates two excitation voltage waveforms, which are fed to two power amplifiers via a waveform generator. The power amplifiers supply the windings of the field generating yokes. The dB/dt and dH/dt signals, amplified by a factor 100, are fed to the oscilloscope, A/D converted, and transferred to the software, to calculate B , H , and the energy loss, enabling the waveform controller to update excitation voltage waveforms.

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RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The hysteresis loops and losses were measured in the frequency range $5 \text{ Hz} \leq f \leq 200 \text{ Hz}$, with the peak polarization J_p spanning from 1 T to 1.5 T. The reference alternating loss values, obtained at INRIM with an Epstein frame, following the IEC 60404-2 standard, have been supplemented by tests performed at the SATIE Laboratory (CNRS/ENS), where the effective field and the induction were measured by localized H - and B -coils, respectively, placed at center of the one of the Epstein frame arm (i.e., with the calibrated H-coil directly placed on the strip surface, and the B-coil wound around it). A very good agreement was verified between the loss figures obtained with the local method and the conventional approach following the IEC 60404-2 Standard, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Table I shows that the differences of the loss figures obtained by the two methods range between -0.4% and 0.6% at 50 Hz, to attain a maximum value around 2.5% at 200 Hz. We conclude that the search for the absolute accuracy of the RSST method can be solidly referred to the measurements made at the same frequency and peak polarization J_p with the standard Epstein frame.

TABLE I – RELATIVE DIFFERENCES (%) BETWEEN ALTERNATING LOSS VALUES OBTAINED WITH THE STANDARD EPSTEIN METHOD (IEC 60404-2) AND WITH LOCAL H - AND B -COILS PLACED AT THE CENTER OF ONE ARM OF THE EPSTEIN FRAME.

Frequency	$J_p = 1 \text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25 \text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4 \text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5 \text{ T}$
20	2.12	0.25	1.25	-0.69
50	-0.05	-0.40	0.59	0.60
100	0.71	-0.78	-0.46	-1.53
200	-1.32	-1.48	-2.75	-2.48

Figure 5. Energy loss vs. frequency and peak polarization obtained by means of measurements carried out with the standard Epstein frame (solid lines) and with the local H - and B -coils (dashed lines)

Employing the above-described RSST, INRIM performed preliminary tests on disk-shaped samples to investigate the influence of the sensing area dimension. A set of measurements under alternating flux was performed, and the results were compared to the reference Epstein figures. A sensing area of $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ (both H - and B -coils) was first adopted. By comparing the outcomes of this arrangement with the Epstein frame results, we attain in the 0.30 mm thick NO Fe–Si strip the situation summarized in Figure 6a. Because of the substantial scattering of the results, a sensing area of $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$, with accordingly sized H - and B -coils, was adopted. It provided better agreement, as shown in Fig. 6b. At 50 Hz and 100 Hz, the relative differences ranged between -1% and -8%. The $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$ coil arrangement was therefore adopted for the interlaboratory comparison.

Figure 6. Comparison of alternating energy loss measured at INRIM up to 200 Hz at $1 \text{ T} \leq J_p \leq 1.5 \text{ T}$ in 0.30 mm thick NO Fe–Si strip by the Epstein frame method and the RSST setup developed at INRIM. a) Sensing area $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$. b) Sensing area $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$. At 50 Hz, the relative differences range between 2% and 10% for the larger area and between -1% and -8% for the smaller one. The scattering of the results with the frequency is reduced by adopting the smaller measuring region.

Interlaboratory results and comparison

Figure 7 provides a set of energy loss versus frequency behaviors $W(f)$ obtained in the different labs for $1 \text{ T} \leq J_p \leq 1.5 \text{ T}$ under alternating and circular flux up to 200 Hz. The Epstein frame results (IEC 60404-2) are provided as a reference.

The alternating loss figures are provided in Tables II, III, and IV, while in Table V the best values of the measured loss figures, obtained as unweighted averages of the laboratories outcomes, are listed. The Epstein frame results for the alternating losses are given in Table VI.

Fig. 7. Alternating (a) and rotational (b) energy losses measured up to 200 Hz at $1 \text{ T} \leq J_p \leq 1.5 \text{ T}$ in 0.30 mm thick NO Fe–Si sheets on circular (INRIM, Ampère) and cross-shaped (PoliTO) samples. The Epstein figures are provided as a reference for the alternating induction.

Energy loss under alternating field (sinusoidal $J(t)$)

TABLE II – ALTERNATING LOSS FIGURES OBTAINED BY THE RSST SETUP AT INRIM

Frequency	$J_p = 1 \text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25 \text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4 \text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5 \text{ T}$
5	14.3	21.0	26.7	31.9
10	14.9	21.8	27.8	33.1
20	15.6	23.0	29.4	35.2
50	17.5	26.0	33.1	40.3
100	20.7	30.6	38.9	46.7
200	26.3	38.7	49.2	58.3

TABLE III – ALTERNATING LOSS FIGURES OBTAINED BY THE RSST SETUP AT AMPÈRE LAB.

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	16.6	23.7	29.8	33.9
10	16.9	24.3	30.1	35.6
20	17.6	25.4	31.9	37.6
50	19.5	28.3	35.5	41.8
100	22.1	32.5	41.1	49.9
200	27.1	40.3	50.9	61.0

TABLE IV – ALTERNATING LOSS FIGURES OBTAINED BY THE RSST SETUP AT POLITO

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	15.6	23.2	28.2	31.8
10	16.4	23.4	29.0	33.8
20	17.0	24.7	30.9	35.5
50	19.3	28.1	33.6	39.3
100	22.8	32.7		
200	28.8	41.0		

TABLE V – BEST VALUES OF THE ALTERNATING LOSS FIGURES, THE AVERAGE OF THE VALUES PROVIDED BY THE PARTICIPATING LABORATORIES

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	15.5	22.6	28.2	32.6
10	16.1	23.2	29.0	34.2
20	16.7	24.4	30.7	36.1
50	18.8	27.4	34.1	40.4
100	21.9	31.9	40.0	48.3
200	27.4	40.0	50.0	59.6

TABLE VI – THE ALTERNATING LOSS VALUES WERE OBTAINED WITH A STANDARD EPSTEIN FRAME. THEY PLAY THE ROLE OF REFERENCE VALUES

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	14.45	22.22	29.80	34.66
10	14.90	22.87	30.58	35.31
20	15.65	24.08	32.04	37.19
50	17.65	27.10	36.06	42.00
100	20.57	31.53	41.88	48.90
200	25.58	39.58	52.25	61.27

Tables VII, VIII, and IX list the relative (%) differences of the alternating loss figures measured with the Epstein frame and with the RSST setup by each laboratory. The best values, defined as the unweighted averages of the individual RSST figures at defined J_p and f values, are compared with the corresponding reference values and the relative differences are given in Table X. Such differences are included in the maximum interval $\pm 7\%$.

TABLE VII – PERCENT DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE RSST INRIM VALUES AND THE EPSTEIN REFERENCE VALUES

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	-1.0	-5.8	-11.6	-8.5
10	0.0	-5.0	-9.9	-6.7
20	-0.6	-4.6	-8.9	-5.7
50	-1.1	-4.4	-9.0	-4.3
100	0.6	-3.1	-7.7	-4.6
200	2.6	-2.3	-6.2	-5.1

TABLE VIII – PERCENT DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE RSST AMPÈRE LAB VALUES AND THE EPSTEIN REFERENCE VALUES

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	14.9	6.6	-0.1	-2.1
10	13.4	6.2	-1.5	0.9
20	12.3	5.3	-0.4	1.0
50	10.6	4.4	-1.6	-0.6
100	7.6	3.0	-1.8	2.0
200	5.9	1.9	-2.6	-0.5

TABLE IX – PERCENT DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE RSST POLITO LAB VALUES AND THE EPSTEIN REFERENCE VALUES

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	7.8	4.4	-5.4	-8.1
10	10.3	2.3	-5.1	-4.4
20	8.8	2.6	-3.6	-4.5
50	9.4	3.6	-6.8	-6.4
100	10.6	3.7		
200	12.7	3.5		

TABLE X – PERCENT DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE BEST VALUES OF THE RSST LOSS FIGURES, THE UNWEIGHTED AVERAGE OF THE INDIVIDUAL LABORATORY OUTCOMES, AND THE EPSTEIN REFERENCE VALUES

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	7.22	1.84	-5.29	-6.03
10	7.88	1.25	-5.22	-3.23
20	6.81	1.15	-4.07	-2.95
50	6.32	1.25	-5.56	-3.69
100	6.27	1.21	-4.48	-1.22
200	7.07	1.01	-4.24	-2.66

The dispersion of the alternating loss figures provided by the individual laboratories around the best values is given in Tables XI, XII, and XIII. It is contained in a $\pm 7\%$ band.

TABLE XI – PERCENT DEVIATIONS OF THE RSST ALTERNATING LOSS OUTCOMES BY INRIM WITH RESPECT TO THE BEST LOSS VALUES.

Frequency	$J_p = 1\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5\text{ T}$
5	-7.7	-7.2	-5.4	-2.0
10	-7.3	-5.9	-4.0	-3.1
20	-7.0	-5.5	-4.3	-2.6
50	-7.0	-5.4	-2.8	-0.5
100	-5.4	-4.2	-2.8	-3.2
200	-4.1	-3.3	-1.7	-2.2

TABLE XII – PERCENT DEVIATIONS OF THE RSST ALTERNATING LOSS OUTCOMES BY AMPÈRE LAB. WITH RESPECT TO THE BEST LOSS VALUES.

Frequency	$J_p = 1\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5\text{ T}$
5	7.2	4.7	5.5	4.2
10	5.1	4.9	3.9	4.3
20	5.1	4.1	3.8	4.1
50	4.1	3.1	4.2	3.2
100	1.2	1.7	2.8	3.2
200	-1.1	0.8	1.7	2.2

TABLE XIII – PERCENT DEVIATIONS OF THE RSST ALTERNATING LOSS OUTCOMES BY POLITO LAB. WITH RESPECT TO THE BEST LOSS VALUES.

Frequency	$J_p = 1\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5\text{ T}$
5	0.5	2.5	-0.1	-2.2
10	2.2	1.0	0.1	-1.2
20	1.8	1.4	0.5	-1.6
50	2.9	2.3	-1.4	-2.8
100	4.1	2.4		
200	5.3	2.4		

Energy loss under rotating field (circular polarization loci)

The Tables XIV – XVI provide the rotational loss figures measured by INRIM, Ampère Lab, and PoliTo, from 5 Hz to 200 Hz at the peak polarization values 1.0, 1.25, 1.4, and 1.5 T. The best values, obtained as unweighted averages of the loss figures obtained by the individual laboratories are given in Table XVII. The deviations of these figures from the best values are listed in Tables XVIII, XIX, and XX. They are contained in a $\pm 5\%$ band.

TABLE XIV– ROTATIONAL LOSS VALUES OBTAINED BY INRIM

Frequency	$J_p = 1\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5\text{ T}$
5	24.4	30.8	37.0	41.9
10	25.0	31.8	38.2	43.3
20	26.3	34.0	40.8	45.7
50	30.2	39.3	47.3	53.5
100	35.9	47.5	57.3	64.7
200	46.5	62.6	76.6	86.7

TABLE XV– ROTATIONAL LOSS VALUES OBTAINED BY AMPERE LAB.

Frequency	$J_p = 1\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5\text{ T}$
5	26.4	33.7	40.7	45.5
10	26.8	34.4	42.2	47.3
20	28.2	36.8	44.1	49.4
50	32.3	42.4	50.4	57.4
100	37.1	50.1	60.9	68.1
200	47.2	65.3	79.9	90.9

TABLE XVI – ROTATIONAL LOSS VALUES OBTAINED BY POLITO.

Frequency	$J_p = 1\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5\text{ T}$
5	26.3	34.0	38.6	
10	27.0	35.0	40.6	
20	28.1	36.6	42.8	
50	32.2	41.8	48.4	
100	39.1	50.2		
200	49.6	64.7		

TABLE XVII – BEST VALUES OF THE ROTATIONAL LOSS FIGURES. THEY ARE OBTAINED AS THE UNWEIGHTED AVERAGES OF THE LOSS FIGURES OBTAINED BY THE INDIVIDUAL LABORATORIES

Frequency	$J_p = 1\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.25\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.4\text{ T}$	$J_p = 1.5\text{ T}$
5	25.7	32.8	38.8	43.7
10	26.3	33.7	40.3	45.3
20	27.5	35.8	42.6	47.6
50	31.6	41.2	48.7	55.5
100	37.4	49.2	59.1	66.4
200	47.8	64.2	78.3	88.8

TABLE XVIII – RELATIVE DEVIATIONS (%) FROM THE BEST VALUES OF THE ROTATIONAL LOSS VALUES OBTAINED BY INRIM.

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	-5.2	-6.2	-4.7	-4.1
10	-5.0	-5.8	-5.4	-4.4
20	-4.5	-5.0	-4.2	-3.9
50	-4.3	-4.6	-2.9	-3.5
100	-4.0	-3.6	-3.0	-2.6
200	-2.6	-2.5	-2.1	-2.4

TABLE XIX – RELATIVE DEVIATIONS (%) FROM THE BEST VALUES OF THE ROTATIONAL LOSS VALUES OBTAINED BY AMPERE LAB.

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	2.7	2.7	5.0	4.1
10	2.1	2.0	4.7	4.4
20	2.4	2.8	3.6	3.9
50	2.3	3.0	3.5	3.5
100	-0.7	1.8	3.0	2.6
200	-1.2	1.7	2.1	2.4

TABLE XX – RELATIVE DEVIATIONS (%) FROM THE BEST VALUES OF THE ROTATIONAL LOSS VALUES OBTAINED BY POLITO

Frequency	$J_p = 1$ T	$J_p = 1.25$ T	$J_p = 1.4$ T	$J_p = 1.5$ T
5	2.5	3.5	-0.3	
10	2.9	3.8	0.7	
20	2.2	2.2	0.5	
50	2.0	1.6	-0.6	
100	4.7	1.9		
200	3.9	0.8		

CONCLUSIONS

INRIM, Ampère Lab, and Polito engaged in a comparison on the alternating and rotational loss measurements by means of laboratory-developed RSST systems. By this comparison, we can evaluate the progress made with respect to the previous exercise carried out in the '90s, which showed large lab-to-lab deviations of the measured rotational loss figures, running up to about 40 % [10]. The experiments were performed on 0.30 mm thick non-oriented Fe-(3.5 wt%)Si steel sheets from 5 Hz to 200 Hz and peak polarization values ranging between 1.0 T and 1.5 T. Alternating loss measurements, made by associating the Epstein test frame method with the H-coil method, permitted one to achieve a full sequence of reference values, by which the best values of the loss figures generated by the comparison and their deviations from the reference provide the participating laboratories with quantitative proof of the measuring capability achievable by use of their RSST setup. It is shown that deviations of the best RSST alternating loss values and the reference ones are contained in a band of ± 7 %. At the same time, it is obtained that the relative deviations of the rotational loss figures obtained in the different laboratories attain at most values around ± 5 %.

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